

ARTISTIC DEFINITION OF THE TYPES OF CALLIGRAPHY IN NASIMI'S WORK

K. Heydarova,
ANAS Institute of Linguistics named after Nasimi
Head of the Department of History of the Azerbaijani language
PhD in Philology, Associate Professor

Annotatsiya. *Botiniy, so'fiy, adabiy, tasavvufiy qarashlari bilan o'zining tug'ma she'riy tasavvurini aruz metrda ajoyib tarzda namoyon eta olgan buyuk ozarbayjon shoiri Imodiddin Nasimiy (1369-1417) o'z ijodida so'fiy adabiyotining ramziy ma'nosiga keng o'rin bergan. Inson qiyofasini madh etar ekan, so'zlarni g'arazli ma'noda o'ynagan shoir arab alifbosining xattotlik turlari: muhaqqoq, qubar, nasx, tulus, rayhon nomlarini tilga oladi.*

Резюме. *Имадеддин Насими (1369-1417), великий азербайджанский поэт, который смог удивительным образом продемонстрировать свое врожденное поэтическое воображение с его батином, тасаввуфом, хуруфом и мистическими взглядами, уделил особое внимание символике литературы тасаввуфа в своем творчестве. Поэт, который играл словами в скрытых смыслах, упоминал виды каллиграфии арабского алфавита, такие как мухаккак, губаар, насх, сулюс и райхани, прославляя при этом человеческий образ.*

Abstract. *Imadaddin Nasimi (1369-1417), the great Azerbaijani poet who was able to demonstrate his innate poet's imagination with his batin, tasawwuf, huruf and mystical views in an amazing way, paid special attention to the symbolism of Tasawwuf literature in his work. The poet who played on words in hidden meanings mentioned types of calligraphy of the Arabic alphabet such as Muhaqqaq, Ghubaar, Naskh, Thuluth and Rayhani while glorifying the human image.*

Kalit so'zlar. *Muhaqqoq, qubar, nasx, tulus, rayhon.*

Ключевые слова. *Мухаккак, губаар, насх, сулюс и райхани.*

Keywords. *Muhaqqaq, Ghubaar, Naskh, Thuluth and Rayhani*

Imadaddin Nasimi (1369-1417), the great Azerbaijani poet who was able to demonstrate his innate poet's imagination with his batin, tasawwuf, huruf and mystical views in an amazing way, paid special attention to the symbolism of Tasawwuf literature in his work. The poet who played on words in hidden meanings mentioned types of calligraphy of the Arabic alphabet such as *Muhaqqaq, Ghubaar, Naskh, Thuluth* and *Rayhani* while glorifying the human image. Fazlullah Naimi, the founder of Hurufism, believed that Adam's face is al-Lawh al-Mahfuz, i.e. a book of God, and ism-i azam, i.e. a prayer that is the totality of God's blessed names. Because Adam's face bears the signs of the name of the God or the 32 divine words from the ism-i azam (32 letters of the Persian alphabet in which the "Javidanname", the holy book of the Hurufis, is written). Another reason is that the 14 lines on Adam's face correspond to the 14 letters (لام لام الف هي الف) appearing from the God's name (الله). See: [8, p. 256].

"Xalü xətü zülfü anın can Müshəfidir oxuram,

Gördüm mühəqqəq biqubar ol nəsx ilə reyhan gəlir” [3, p. 202]

The poet showed here that the fine hairs (xalü xət) on the hair (zülf) and face are the script of the Qur’an (Mushaf). Four types of calligraphy are mentioned in the second verse: Muhaqqaq, Ghubaar, Naskh and Rayhani. These types of calligraphy are among the main six types of calligraphy (*Naskh, Thuluth, Muhaqqaq, Rayhani, Ruqa, Tawqi*) that Abu Ali Muhammad Ibn Ali al-Husayn (al-Hasan) Ibn Muqla al-Baghdadi (d. 328/940) identified and improved. The meaning of the word *Muhaqqaq* (in Arabic محقق) means justice, reality, proven truth, verified, true. We can also find moments in Nasimi’s poems that express the meanings of “*probably, undoubtedly, rightly, truly*” as parenthetical words:

“İki aləmdəsən Sultani-Mütləq,

Fətəhna şə’ninə gəldi mühəqqəq” [3, p. 103]

Besides Thuluth and Naskh, the Muhaqqaq script was also used in Qur’anic texts until the 16th century. Its writing feature is characterized by longer lines than the Thuluth line. This type of calligraphy was written with a reed pen with a tip width of about 2 mm, and the letters and words were written clearly.

Nasimi stated in the following verse that there is divine light and the Absolute essence (Nuri-mütləq) in Adam’s face, and he used the word muhaqqaq in the meaning of “without doubt” and to express the type of calligraphy by playing on words again:

Nuri-mütləq, zati-mütləq səndədir.

Müshəfin hərfi mühəqqəq səndədir [2, p. 268]

One of the most used types of calligraphy of “Al-Aqlam Al-Sittah” is *Naskh*. S. Nematzadeh, who gave information about this type of calligraphy, wrote: “*The pen thickness of the Naskh is one third of a Thuluth (1mm). Naskh was mostly used for writing books and mushafs (folded paper), and Rayhani was completely eliminated after the 16th century. Today, the Naskh script is preferred due to its ease of reading and writing in the Islamic world*” [4, p. 17-18].

When Nasimi said, “*Gördüm mühəqqəq biqubar ol nəsx ilə reyhan gəlir*” [3, p. 202]

“Xey – Xətindən utanır nəsx ilə reyhanü sülüs,

Ta mühəqqəq ana manənd olalı xəttü qubar” [3, p. 218]

To be *naskhed* means to be annulled, to be eliminated, to be released without sentence. “To eliminate the verdict or words of any Sharia evidence with evidence of the Qur’an and Sunnah” (Muhammad ibn Salih al-Uthaymin’s book “al-Usul min Ilm al-Usul” p. 51).

“Neçə xət əhlini qubar edənin,

Nəsx olundu xətində reyhanı” [3, p. 218]

The Rayhani mentioned in the second verse, which was taken from the name of *reyhan* (basil) and is an annual cultivated plant with a pleasant smell, decorative, and some species of which can be eaten, was widely used as a type of calligraphy in writing the Qur’an and prayers. The letters in the Rayhani script look like leaves, and the writing looks like floral patterns. Many romantic prose examples, epics with many images of nature and verse stories were written with Rayhani script [İlgar Fahmi, p. 69].

“*Surətin yazusu reyhan, Həq dəbir,
Həm səm’i-bibədəlsən, həm bəsir*” [3, p. 273]

“*Xey – Xətindən utanır nəsx ilə reyhanü sülüs,
Ta mühəqqəq ana manənd olalı xəttü qubar*” [3, p. 218]

Thuluth (ثلث) is the oldest type of calligraphy, which is written with a reed pen with a tip width of 3 mm and was used extensively in qita, beit, qasida and Qur’anic manuscripts.

The word *Ghubaar* (غبار) means dust, fine soil in Arabic. According to the generally accepted opinion, the small writing form of each type of script is called *Ghubaar*. But even so, it is said to be more similar to *Nastaliq* and *Riqa* scripts. The *Ghubaar* script was used to write verses and hadiths in letters, which were tied to pigeons, in small Qur’an books that could be carried in the pocket, and inside large letters in the past.

“*Neçə xətlə əhlini qubar edənin,
Nəsx olundu xətdə reyhanı*” [3, p. 237]

Nasimi also used the word *biqubar* in his ghazal. Here *ə* is prefixed *with* in Arabic and means “with *ghubaar*”.

“*Xalü xəttü zülfü anın can müshəfidir oxuram,
Gördüm mühəqqəq biqubar ol nəsx ilə reyhan gəlir*” [3, p. 202]

The poet, who considered the appearance of a human as a living Qur’an, said that he read it and created his artistic descriptions by showing that these writings were written in *Ghubaar*, *Muhaqqaq*, *Naskh* and *Reyhani* scripts. The poet compared the delicate hairs in the mustache to the types of calligraphy in the following couplets: “*dodağın xətti*”, “*xəti reyhan göyərmiş Kövsər üstünə*”, “*lə’li-ləbin reyhandır xətin*” means a mustache (line) on the lip. Here, there is an associative relationship between the line of calligraphy and “*xətt*” (line), which means a delicate fluffy mustache.

“*Bənzədirlər dodağın xəttini reyhana, vəli,
Şol zümürüüd göhərin qiymətin əf’a nə bilür?*” [3, p. 137]

Glorifying the types of calligraphy in the human face is observed as a tradition in medieval *Tasawwuf* literature. For example, the ruler-poet *Gazi Burhaneddin*, who lived in the 14th century, mentioned the *Rayhani*, *Muhaqqaq*, and *Naskh* scripts in the following verses and associated them with the appearance of a human:

“*Xəttünə əgərçi yüzünün sülsini tutdı,
Gülşəndə bəgüm dəsteyi-reyhan necə bənzər*” [3, p. 29]

“*Zülfün ki qılır nəsx qamu xətti mühəqqəq,
Oxımağa yarar idi, zirü-zəbər olsa*” [3, p. 654]

The same trend is observed in *Gulshani* in the 15th century, *Khalifa* and *Shah Ismail Khatai* in the 16th century:

“*Yazmadın nunü qələm lövh üzrə xətti-kainat
Nurdən safi bəyazun nəsxə eyn idi, məqim*” [7, p. 245]

“*Şəha, dildən gübari nəsx edən reyhani-xəttindir,
Mühəqqəq bəndəniz, qırma bizi mişkin rəqəmlərlə*” [1, p. 330]

“*Dil yazdı mühəqqəq ol nişanı,
Nəsx etməyə xətti-reyhan anı*” [6, p. 289]

But none of them paid as much attention to the divine essence of writings on human's face as Nasimi, carried out ideological propaganda such as hiding Hurufi ideas in lines and letters, and identified the perfect human with God so much.

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